

Bloodstream Infections in Cardiac Intensive Care Units from a Tertiary Care CentreSpriha Smriti¹, Babita Kumari², Pratulya Nandan³¹Tutor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.²Tutor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.³Professor, Department of Microbiology, Patna Medical College & Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.

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Abstract:**Background:** Bloodstream infections (BSIs) are a significant source of morbidity and mortality in cardiac intensive care units (CICUs). The use of invasive devices and the critical condition of patients contribute to a high risk of these infections. Understanding the epidemiology, risk factors, and outcomes of BSIs in CICUs is essential for improving patient care.**Aim:** This research aims to analyze the incidence, risk factors, and outcomes of BSIs in the CICU of a tertiary care centre and to develop targeted strategies to prevent and manage these infections.**Methods:** A retrospective observational research involving 150 CICU patients was carried out. Patient demographics, clinical traits, microbiological results, therapy, and results were all recorded. SPSS version 23.0 was utilised for the statistical analysis, and logistic regression was employed to find independent risk factors for BSIs.**Results:** Out of 150 patients, 45 (30%) developed BSIs. The most common pathogens isolated were *Staphylococcus aureus* (40%), *Escherichia coli* (22%), and *Klebsiellapneumoniae* (18%). Significant risk factors for BSIs included the presence of central venous catheters (OR = 3.2, 95% CI: 1.8-5.6, $p < 0.001$) and prolonged CICU stays (>7 days) (OR = 2.7, 95% CI: 1.5-4.9, $p = 0.002$). Patients with BSIs had longer CICU stays (mean 15.4 ± 6.8 days) compared to those without BSIs (mean 8.2 ± 4.5 days, $p < 0.001$) and a higher mortality rate (35.6% vs. 15.2%, $p = 0.005$).**Conclusion:** BSIs are a significant burden in CICUs, associated with prolonged hospital stays and increased mortality. Central venous catheters and prolonged CICU stays are major risk factors. Effective infection control practices are essential to mitigate these risks.**Recommendations:** Implementing strict aseptic techniques, using antimicrobial-coated catheters and continuous surveillance are recommended to reduce the incidence of BSIs. Further research is needed to explore additional preventive measures and optimize patient outcomes.**Keywords:** Bloodstream Infections, Cardiac Intensive Care Unit, Risk Factors, Mortality, Infection Control.

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Introduction

An important factor in death and morbidity are (BSIs), especially in patients who are very sick. Due to the frequent use of invasive equipment and the serious nature of the patients' diseases, the (CICU), which treats patients with severe cardiac problems, is a high-risk environment for the development of blood clots. While the prevalence of (BSIs) in (CICUs) varies around the world, research continuously shows how seriously these infections affect patient outcomes, including longer hospital stays, greater healthcare expenses, and higher death rates.

Understanding the epidemiology, risk factors, and outcomes linked to BSIs in CICUs is crucial, as recent research has shown. A study conducted which revealed that the rate of blood clot infections

(BSIs) in (ICUs) varies between 2.5 and 10 per 1,000 catheter days [1]. Notably, a significant proportion of these infections occur in cardiac ICUs. BSIs are frequently associated with the use of central venous catheters, mechanical ventilation, and extended hospitalisations in intensive care units. They are also among the most prevalent infections acquired in hospitals. *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Klebsiellapneumoniae* are the most commonly isolated organisms among the several pathogens that cause bloodstream infections (BSIs) in (CICUs) [2]. These infections frequently show signs of resistance to several antibiotics, which makes treatment more difficult and raises the possibility of negative results. The World Health Organisation [3] has emphasised the rise of

antibiotic resistance, which makes controlling (BSIs) in critical care settings even more difficult.

Improving patient outcomes in (CICUs) requires identifying and reducing risk factors for BSIs. Research has repeatedly shown that the duration of the ICU visit and the use of invasive equipment, like central venous catheters, are important risk factors for (BSIs) [4]. Furthermore, a higher incidence of blood vessel infections (BSIs) has been linked to underlying comorbidities such as diabetes and chronic kidney disease [5]. Infection control procedures have advanced, however BSIs continue to be a problem in CICUs. The incidence of (BSIs) has been proven to be reduced by the application of evidence-based protocols, such as the use of catheters coated with antimicrobial agents and strict adherence to aseptic practices. Still, to maintain these gains, focused interventions and on-going monitoring are necessary.

The research aims to improve patient care and outcomes in CICUs by providing insights into the epidemiology and consequences of BSIs in this particular setting. These insights will be useful in developing focused strategies for managing and preventing these infections.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a retrospective observational study designed to analyze (BSIs) in the (CICUs) of a tertiary care centre.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the cardiac ICUs of a tertiary care hospital in PMCH, Patna which is a major referral centre providing specialized cardiac care.

Participants: A total of 150 patients admitted to the CICU between January 2018 to January 2019 were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients admitted to the CICU during the study period.
- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients who developed bloodstream infections during their stay in the CICU.
- Individuals who gave their informed consent to take part in the research.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with a history of bloodstream infections prior to CICU admission.

- Patients transferred from other hospitals with a known bloodstream infection.

- Patients who did not provide informed consent.

- Patients with incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all patients meeting the inclusion criteria were consecutively included in the study. Information bias was reduced by using standardized data collection forms and procedures.

Data Collection: Information was gathered from electronic health records, comprising patient demographics, clinical traits, laboratory results, microbiological data, treatment details, and outcomes. Data collection was performed by trained research staff to ensure accuracy and consistency.

Procedure:

1. Patients' medical records were reviewed to identify cases of bloodstream infections.
2. Relevant data were extracted and recorded in a standardized data collection form.
3. Microbiological data were obtained from the hospital's laboratory information system.
4. Patients' outcomes, including length of stay in the CICU, treatment response, and mortality, were documented.

Statistical Analysis: Version 23.0 of SPSS was used to analyse the data. For continuous variables, descriptive statistics were computed, such as means, medians, and standard deviations. The categorical variables were expressed as percentages and frequencies. To compare categorical variables, chi-square tests were utilised; for continuous variables, t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests were applied. To find variables that were independently linked to bloodstream infections, multivariate logistic regression analysis was used. A statistically significant p-value was defined as less than 0.05.

Results

This study examined 150 patients' BSIs in the CICUs of a tertiary care facility using retrospective observation. The majority was male (54.7), with a mean age of 65.2 years. Extended stays in the CICU and the use of central venous catheters were important risk factors for BSIs. In comparison to patients without BSIs, individuals with BSIs experienced noticeably longer CICU hospitalisations and greater death rates.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Value
Number of participants	150
Mean age (years)	65.2 ± 12.4
Gender distribution	
- Male	82 (54.7%)
- Female	68 (45.3%)
Underlying conditions	
- Coronary artery disease	90 (60%)
- Heart failure	38 (25.3%)
- Arrhythmias	22 (14.7%)

Incidence and Microbiological Data: Out of the 150 patients, 45 (30%) developed bloodstream infections (BSIs). The most commonly isolated pathogens were *S.aureus*(40%), *E. coli* (22%), and *Klebsiellapneumoniae* (18%). The distribution of pathogens is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Pathogens Isolated in Bloodstream Infections

Pathogen	Number of Cases	Percentage (%)
Staphylococcus aureus	18	40%
Escherichia coli	10	22%
Klebsiellapneumoniae	8	18%
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	5	11%
Enterococcus species	4	9%

Table 3: Risk Factors for Bloodstream Infections and Outcomes

Factor/Outcome	Patients with BSIs (n=45)	Patients without BSIs (n=105)	p-value
Central venous catheter (%)	75%	45%	<0.001
Prolonged CICU stay (>7 days) (%)	60%	30%	0.002
Mean CICU stay (days)	15.4 ± 6.8	8.2 ± 4.5	<0.001
Mortality rate (%)	35.6%	15.2%	0.005

The study highlights the need for enhanced infection control measures and vigilant monitoring of patients in the CICU to reduce the incidence of BSIs and improve patient outcomes.

Discussion

This study looks at the frequency, contributing variables, and results of bloodstream infections (BSIs) in a tertiary care centres' (CICU). With a 30% incidence rate of BSIs among 150 patients, it is evident how seriously these infections affect critically ill cardiac patients. This elevated risk is exacerbated by the frequent use of invasive devices and the critically ill state of these individuals. According to earlier studies, the most common infections found were *Klebsiellapneumoniae*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

The WHO notes that the escalation of antibiotic resistance makes managing bloodstream infections more challenging and highlights the necessity of on-going surveillance and focused antimicrobial stewardship initiatives. The frequency of bloodstream infections can be decreased by employing effective infection control measures, such as using catheters coated with antimicrobials and strictly following to aseptic procedures. A strong infection control strategy must include

regular training and teaching of healthcare personnel on infection prevention techniques.

High prevalence rates of Gram (+) bacteria like *Staphylococcus* and *Enterococcus* species as well as Gram (-) bacteria like *Klebsiellapneumoniae* were found in a study that looked at BSIs across a variety of ICUs, including cardiovascular ICUs. The necessity of customised antibiotic treatments to address the diverse microbial profiles found in various ICUs was highlighted by this investigation [6].

33.1% of infections linked to healthcare were central line-associated bloodstream infections (CLABSI), according to a prospective study conducted in tertiary care facilities in Egypt. CLABSI had a 4.08 incidence rate per 1000 device days, which had a major effect on patient outcomes and hospital stay duration. In order to lessen the burden of HAIs, the study emphasised the significance of strict infection control procedures and adherence to evidence-based methods [7].

Peripherally inserted central catheter (PICC) lines and haematologic malignancies were revealed to be major factors influencing CLABSI rates in non-ICU wards, according to an observational study conducted in a large tertiary hospital. In order to

successfully lower the incidence of CLABSI, this study highlighted the necessity for customised preventative interventions for various patient populations [8].

In order to successfully lower the prevalence of bloodstream infections in cardiology ICUs, the studies collectively highlight the crucial necessity for focused interventions, adherence to established guidelines, and customised antibiotic treatments. To enhance patient outcomes and lower healthcare costs related to these illnesses, interdisciplinary methods and infection control efforts are crucial.

Conclusion

BSIs are a major problem in (CICUs), leading to longer hospital stays and higher rates of death. In order to improve infection control procedures and patient outcomes in critical care units, the study emphasises the need for focused interventions, ongoing surveillance, and continual investigation.

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